

DIRECTIONS OF BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN RURAL AREAS

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ABSTRACT

In our article, which is brought to the attention of the readers, the reforms carried out today in Uzbekistan regarding the development of entrepreneurship, the issues of providing employment to the temporarily unemployed population living in rural areas, the creation of comfortable living conditions for the population in rural areas, as well as scientific proposals for increasing the population's income and practical recommendations are given.

Introduction. The reforms implemented in our country to create a stable and efficient economy are showing their results today. In particular, significant progress is being made in implementing deep structural changes in the economy, ensuring the growth of the population's income, strengthening effective foreign trade and investment processes, sustainable development of small business and private entrepreneurship, and strengthening the banking and financial system.

The prestige and position of our country in the international economic arena is growing significantly and regularly. In this case, the socio-economic development strategy has been carefully developed, the goals and tasks of economic reforms, and the ways of implementation have been clearly and correctly indicated.

Small enterprises and micro-firms are mainly focused on the main factor in the formation of a competitive environment that ensures the modern level of the country's production, in the fight against monopoly, and in the practical application of scientific and technical achievements.

During the visit of the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Namangan region on March 25, 2024, he defined the implementation of many programs for the further development of the Namangan region. It was emphasized that large-scale economic reforms should be implemented in the province. In particular, the untapped potential of some districts in the region, issues of further development of specialized drivers of each district were considered and tasks were defined.

The main focus in this direction is to develop small business and entrepreneurship in rural areas, and for this purpose, to develop the activities of small industrial zones, to provide them with comprehensive support, to identify and support young people who want to start and develop their own entrepreneurship. importance was emphasized.

Material and methods. Today, a lot of research is being conducted on the establishment and development of small industrial zones in rural areas, and many issues identified during the research are being solved. It is necessary to use the most effective research methods to find solutions to identified and unsolved problems. In particular, methods such as observation, generalization, grouping, comparative analysis, questionnaire survey, expert evaluation of results, economic analysis and economic-statistical methods are effective in conducting research.

These methods make it possible to generalize the approaches and opinions expressed by scientists, to identify existing problems in this regard as a result of data analysis.

Analysis and results.

The development of our country's economy is directly related to the development of small enterprises. If the world population is projected to increase steadily, the sharp increase in the demand for agricultural development in itself represents an increase in the problems related to increasing the level of resource productivity.

As part of the implementation of the Development Strategy in Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, it is planned to halve the poverty level in the country by the end of 2026. The task of ensuring macroeconomic stability and stable economic growth at a high rate is set as the main conditions for achieving the set goals.

For the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, comprehensive measures have been developed to fundamentally improve the business environment, to financially support the initiatives of newly established business entities in the regions, and their implementation is being carried out step by step.

We believe that it is appropriate to implement the following tasks in order to attract large segments of the population to entrepreneurship in rural areas:

- creation of a convenient infrastructure for the establishment of business entities in rural areas;
- training the population living in rural areas in entrepreneurship in order to improve their knowledge of entrepreneurship;
- organization of production at the expense of local resources and localization of finished products;
- starting the export of products produced by business entities;
- development of the most optimal simplified methods of checking and controlling the activity of small industrial zones established in rural areas and preventing excessive interference in the activity.

The implementation of these measures will create the basis for the further development of industry in rural areas in the future, due to which not only production, but also service areas will be widely developed.

One of the most urgent issues in the establishment and operation of industrial zones is the issue of financing. Today, our state is implementing large-scale reforms in the development of

business entities in our country. Subsidies are allocated to entrepreneurs, import duties are exempted for the import of imported production technologies, preferential loans are allocated by commercial banks.

Foreign investment funds are considered to be the most effective means of financing the activities of business entities today. The reason is that attracting long-term investment funds in the activity ensures the achievement of strategic goals. It also increases the possibility of exporting the manufactured products abroad.

Organization of small industrial zones also aims to unite entrepreneurs. While implementing such large projects in rural areas, it is an important issue to organize its control. For this, it is advisable to organize the following activities:

- permanent provision of modern interactive public services from a distance;
- establishment of services of qualified experts on contracts and reports, etc.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be noted that we should effectively use the opportunities provided by our state to develop entrepreneurship in our country. Taking into account that the development of entrepreneurship in rural areas is of great importance in ensuring the stability of the country's economy, it is necessary to ensure the rational and efficient use of convenient infrastructures and rich resources in rural areas, and to use the opportunities to turn them into a source of great income in the future.

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